

Condition of Silver Chromate, Silver Iodide and Lead Iodide in Gelatine.

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When one considers the various theories that have been put forward by different investigators to explain the formation of Liesegang rings, it becomes quite clear that a knowledge about the condition—ionic, colloidal, etc., of the substances deposited in the bands will be of great help in understanding the process of periodic precipitation.

Williams and Mackenzie (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 844), Bolam and Mackenzie (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1926, 22, 162; 1928, 24, 50) and Bolam and Donaldson (*ibid.*, 1933, 29, 864) have shown by *e. m. f.* and conductivity measurements that prior to the appearance of the red colour, the activity of the silver ion in the yellow mixture is very much higher than in a pure saturated solution of silver chromate at the same temperature, and that when the red colour appears the activity of the silver ion simultaneously decreases to a marked extent. Desai and Nabar (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1932, 28, 449) have shown from electrometric measurements that the activity of silver ion in a mixture of silver nitrate and potassium chromate in gelatine remains constant for some minutes, then rapidly decreases and finally becomes constant, and that the point at which the activity commences to fall corresponds in every case with the first appearance of red colour. These experiments lead to the conclusion that the yellow mixture contains silver chromate in supersaturated solution and that the red colour is due to the actual formation of the solid phase, and not to the coagulation of a solid phase which is already present in the form of colloidal particles.

Dhar and collaborators (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 41; *Kolloid Z.*, 1924, 34, 270; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 175; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, 23, 23) have, on the other hand, shown from their electrometric and conductivity measurements that silver chromate is produced in the form of a colloidal solution. According

to them, the yellow mixture contains particles which are negatively charged through adsorption of chromate ions, while the red substance is a less stable sol containing particles which are positively charged through adsorption of silver ions. They have shown that a greater part of silver chromate in gelatine is present in colloidal condition, only about one-third being present in ionic condition. It is difficult to understand why the results of various investigators on the condition of silver chromate in gelatine are so conflicting.

Chatterji and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 177) have shown from *e.m.f.* and conductivity measurements that more than 97% of silver iodide in gelatine exists in condition other than ionic; they believe that it is present in colloidal condition.

Desai and Naik (Paper on "Inhibitive power of Gelatine" which will be published in the September issue of the Journal of the Bombay University, 1933) have shown that the inhibitive power with reference to Ag_2CrO_4 is minimum for gelatine of p_{H} 5.75 and is greater for higher or lower values of p_{H} . In the case of AgI the inhibitive power continuously decreases with a decrease of p_{H} of gelatine. The inhibitive power with reference to PbI_2 is maximum for gelatine of p_{H} 5.0 and is smaller for higher or lower values of p_{H} .

Condition of Silver Chromate in Gelatine.

If yellow solution contains silver chromate in supersaturated solution and not in colloidal condition, one would expect that the conductivity of the yellow mixture should remain the same as that calculated on the basis that all silver chromate exists in ionic condition as long as the colour does not change and that it should gradually decrease with the appearance of the red coloured precipitate. To test this point, a series of conductivity experiments were also undertaken.

The gelatine used in these experiments was the same as used by Desai and Naik (*loc. cit.*) and the p_{H} of gelatine solution was varied in the same manner as done by them. The conductivity was measured by the usual method using an amplifying circuit similar to the one used by Lorenz and Klauer (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1924, 136, 121) (for details please see paper by H. N. Desai, D. B. Naik and B. N. Desai on conductivity measurements in course of publication in *Indian J. Phys.*). The conductivity of the mixture was determined

from time to time. A typical result of conductivity experiments is given in Table I. In Table II is given a summary of all such results obtained with silver chromate.

TABLE I.

Total volume of mixture with conductivity water = 20 c.c. Conc. of gelatine soln. = 3%. pH of gelatine soln. = 5.52. A. Conductivity of 5.5 c.c. gelatine + water = 1.355×10^{-4} . B. Conductivity of 5.5 c.c. gelatine + 5 c.c. N/100-AgNO₃ + water = 4.547×10^{-4} . C. Conductivity of 5.5 c.c. gelatine + 5 c.c. N/100-K₂CrO₄ + water = 4.579×10^{-4} . D. Conductivity of 5.5 c.c. gelatine + 5 c.c. N/100-KNO₃ + water = 4.926×10^{-4} . Temp. = 30°.

Colour of mixture.	Time.	Obs. conductivity (mhos) of mixture 5.5 c.c. gelatine + 5 c.c. N/100-AgNO ₃ + 5 c.c. N/100-K ₂ CrO ₄ + water. E.	Obs. conductivity (mhos) of Ag ₂ CrO ₄ alone. E—D.	Calc. conductivity (mhos) if whole of Ag ₂ CrO ₄ in ionic condition.	% of Ag ₂ CrO ₄ in ionic condition.
				B + C—D—A.	
Yellow	1 min.	6.842×10^{-4}	1.916×10^{-4}	2.845×10^{-4}	67
"	6	6.842	1.916		67
"	10	6.798	1.872		66
"	15	6.842	1.916		67
"	20	6.821	1.895		67
"	25	6.798	1.872		66
"	30	6.821	1.895		67
"	35	6.842	1.916		67
"	40	6.842	1.916		67
"	45	6.798	1.872		66
"	50	6.821	1.895		67
"	55	6.842	1.916		67
First appearance of red colour.	59	6.842	1.916		67
Red	65	6.798	1.872		66
"	70	6.842	1.916		67
"	75	6.821	1.895		67

TABLE II.

pH of gelatine.	Vol. of gelatine.	N/100-AgNO ₃ and N/100-K ₂ CrO ₄ .	Temp. = 30°. Total volume = 20 c.c.		% of Ag ₂ CrO ₄ in ionic condition.
			Obs. conductivity (mhos) of Ag ₂ CrO ₄ alone in mixture.	Calc. conductivity (mhos) if whole of Ag ₂ CrO ₄ in ionic condition.	
			E - D.	B + C - D - A.	
5.52	5.5 c.c.	5 c.c.	1.895 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.845 × 10 ⁻⁴	67
5.52	2.8	4	1.239	1.978	62
5.52	5.0	5	1.260	2.268	56
5.52	6.0	6	1.126	2.576	44
5.52	7.0	6	1.130	2.592	44
4.50	1.25	6	1.889	3.685	51
4.50	1.3	5	1.670	2.561	65
6.00	7.2	6	1.210	2.850	43

It will appear from Table I that when equivalent amounts of AgNO₃ and K₂CrO₄ are added to the same amount of gelatine, the conductivity is slightly less in the former case than in the latter. This is probably due to the fact that more of Ag ions than CrO₄ ions combine with gelatine (*cf.* Bolam and Mackenzie, *loc. cit.*). It will also be seen that the conductivity is reduced more in the presence of K₂CrO₄ than in the presence of an equivalent amount of KNO₃. This will mean that there is greater combination between gelatine and CrO₄ ions than between gelatine and NO₃ ions. An exactly similar behaviour is noticed in all the cases whether pH of gelatine is made smaller or larger than 5.52.

The other and most significant fact noticeable from Table I is that no sooner the solutions are mixed, the conductivity is immediately reduced and thereafter its value does not change even when the red coloured precipitate makes its appearance. Also there is no gradual decrease in the conductivity with the appearance of more and more red coloured precipitate. Whatever changes are to take place in the conductivity occur immediately on mixing the solutions. The same behaviour is noticed when the pH of gelatine

solution is made smaller or larger than 5.52 or when the amount of gelatine is varied keeping the amount of the reactants the same. These results therefore show that (i) the yellow coloured mixture contains some insoluble precipitate of silver chromate and (ii) that the change from the yellow coloured mixture to the red coloured one is not due to release of supersaturation. From the cataphoretic experiments, it is seen that neither the yellow nor red coloured mixture contains any charged particles. It thus appears that the change from the yellow coloured to red coloured mixture is not due to a change in the charge on the particles of the insoluble precipitate formed in the beginning, but simply due to a change in the size of the particles. One can actually see that the particles are invisible in the yellow mixture, while they are sufficiently large to be visible in red coloured mixture. It was also observed that when the reaction is allowed to take place in test tubes and specially when the mixture sets to a gel, the precipitate is first localised at certain points and the mixture ultimately becomes turbid red. A change in the colour due to a change in the size of particles is a very common phenomenon, for example gold sol containing fine particles is ruby red while the one containing larger particles is blue ; one can quote many such instances. It appears that the yellow mixture contains some insoluble precipitate of silver chromate whose particles are in a highly dispersed form, probably even in molecular condition. If the precipitation is molecularly dispersed, it is quite likely that this portion will diffuse at an appreciable rate. This process of diffusion may give rise to union of groups of molecules which may form centres of crystallisation. More of the molecularly dispersed material will, as a result of diffusion, allow the nuclei already formed to grow and thus larger particles, which may be quite visible will, appear. Growth of larger particles at the expense of smaller particles is thus not at all impossible or precluded. The transition from the yellow to red colour will thus be gradual, but in actual practice is noticed only when red coloured fine particles appear.

It will also be seen from Table I that in this particular case about 67% of silver chromate remains in ionic condition and the remaining 33% in a finely dispersed condition in the yellow mixture. As stated before, the colour change from yellow to red does not seem to be due to a sudden release of supersaturation or due to a change in the nature of charge on the colloidal particles.

In all the cases given in Table II, it was also noticed that whatever changes in the conductivity are to take place, occur immediately on mixing the solutions and that the change from the yellow to the red colour is not accompanied by any changes in conductivity. These results, therefore, apparently support the observations of Chatterji (*Proc. Indian Science Congress*, 1932, p. 10) that the *e. m. f.* does not decrease with time with either yellow or red mixtures. It is surprising that the present results do not support either our previous results (Desai and Nabar, *loc. cit.*) or those of Bolam and co-workers (*loc. cit.*). It is, however, a fact that both types of results are based on accurate experiments. Therefore some more work is necessary to find out the conditions favourable for the occurrence of the different behaviours noticed so far.

It will also appear from Table II that by varying the p_H and the concentration of gelatine and of the reactants, the amount of silver chromate which can remain in ionic condition can also be varied; in the present case it has varied from 43 to 67%. In view of this, it is not impossible that under certain circumstances the amount of silver chromate which can remain in ionic condition can be as much as 95% (Nabar and Desai, *Nature*, 1931, 127, 628). It is quite likely that the same causes which are operative in this case might also be responsible for the conflicting results discussed in the previous paragraph. We are of the opinion that if the p_H of gelatine and the concentration of gelatine and of the reactants are such that on mixing the solutions more than 95% of silver chromate can remain in ionic condition, on allowing the mixture to stand the *e. m. f.* or conductivity may not change at all till the colour remains yellow (as observed by Bolam and co-workers, *loc. cit.*, and by Desai and Nabar, *loc. cit.*) and that with the appearance of red colour, the *e. m. f.* and conductivity may change gradually; in such a case the colour change will be due to release of supersaturation. This point is being investigated.

Condition of Silver Iodide in Gelatine.

A typical result of conductivity measurements of silver iodide is given in Table III and a summary of all such results in Table IV.

TABLE III.

Temp. = 30°. Total volume with conductivity water = 20 c.c. Conc. of gelatine soln. used = 3%. p_H of gelatine soln. = 5.52. A. Conductivity of 12 c.c. gelatine + water = 2.746×10^{-4} mhos. B. Conductivity of 12 c.c. gelatine + 3 c.c. N/10-AgNO₃ + water = 1.981×10^{-3} mhos. C. Conductivity of 12 c.c. gelatine + 3 c.c. N/10-KI + water = 2.201×10^{-3} mhos. D. Conductivity of 12 c.c. gelatine + 3 c.c. N/10-KNO₃ + water = 2.245×10^{-3} mhos.

Colour of mixtures.	Time.	Obs. conductivity (mhos) of mixture 12 c.c. gelatine + 3 c.c. N/10-AgNO ₃ + 3 c.c. N/10-KI + water.	Obs. conductivity (mhos) of AgI alone.	Calc. conductivity (mhos) if whole of AgI in ionic condition.	% of AgI in ionic condition.
		E.	E - D.	B + C - D - A.	
Greenish	1 min.	2.259×10^{-3}	0.014×10^{-3}	1.662×10^{-3}	N
	5	2.259	0.014		
	10	2.252	0.007		
	15	2.259	0.014		
	20	2.259	0.014		
Gradual change	25	2.245	...		
	30	2.252	0.007		
	35	2.259	0.014		
	40	2.259	0.014		
	45	2.252	0.007		
Appearance of whitish yellow colour	50	2.252	0.007		
	55	2.252	0.014		

TABLE IV.

Temp. = 30°. Total volume = 20 c.c.

p_H of gelatine.	Vol. of gelatine.	N/100-AgNO ₃ and N/10-KI.	Obs. conductivity (mhos) of AgI alone in mixture. E - D.	Calc. conductivity (mhos) if whole of AgI in ionic condition. B + C - D - A.	% of AgI in ionic condition.
5.52	2.6 c.c.	1 c.c.	0.010×10^{-3}	0.469×10^{-3}	2
5.52	5.2	2	0.017	1.030	2
5.52	8.1	3	0.031	1.706	1
5.52	12.0	3	0.014	1.662	nil
4.50	10.0	3	0.018	1.531	1
4.50	12.0	3	0.022	1.774	nil
6.00	7.2	3	0.012	0.947	1

It will appear from Table III that the conductivity of silver nitrate in gelatine is somewhat smaller than that of an equivalent amount of potassium iodide in gelatine. This again indicates as in the previous case that Ag ions combine more readily with gelatine than CrO_4 ions. Also the conductivity is smaller with potassium iodide in gelatine than with an equivalent amount of potassium nitrate in gelatine. Here there is evidence to show that iodide ions combine more readily with gelatine than nitrate ions. A similar tendency is noticeable in all the experiments whose results are summarised in Table IV.

The colour of the mixture becomes greenish on mixing the solutions of AgNO_3 in gelatine and KI in gelatine. The mixture, however, does not contain any visible particles. On allowing the mixture to stand, the colour gradually changes and with it the mixture also begins to develop turbidity. With the progress of time, the turbidity continuously increases. It will, however, appear from the table that the conductivity changes immediately on mixing the solutions and that it does not change at all thereafter although the colour of the mixture continuously changes and the particles of silver iodide become visible and gradually increase in size. These results therefore show that colour changes are not due to any release of supersaturation.

It will be seen from Tables III and IV that about 98% of silver iodide exists in condition other than ionic. Our results therefore support the results of Chatterji and Dhar (*loc. cit.*) in this respect. They, however, believe that silver iodide in gelatine exists in colloidal condition. To test this point, a series of cataphoretic experiments were undertaken. In no case the presence of charged particles could be detected. We are therefore inclined to the view that silver iodide in gelatine exists in the beginning in a very highly dispersed form probably in molecular condition. As pointed out before, this portion in molecularly dispersed form will, as a result of diffusion, give rise to large particles and the colour changes are due to changes in the size of the particles. As is well known there is always a tendency for larger particles to grow further at the expense of relatively smaller particles.

A change in the p_{π} or in the concentrations of gelatine and the reactants does not very appreciably alter the amount of silver iodide in ionic condition. In this respect silver iodide in gelatine is quite distinct from silver chromate in gelatine. In so far as can be

judged from the present results, the fact that the inhibitive power of gelatine decreases with a decrease of its p_H , does not seem to be of any significance in explaining the results about condition of silver iodide in gelatine.

Condition of Lead Iodide in Gelatine.

A typical result of changes in the conductivity with time in the case of lead iodide in gelatine is given in Table V. A summary of all such experiments is also given in Table VI.

TABLE V.

Temp. = 30°. Total volume with conductivity water = 20 c.c. Conc. of gelatine soln. = 3%. p_H of gelatine = 5.52. A. Conductivity of 9 c.c. gelatine + water = 2.096×10^{-4} mhos. B. Conductivity of 9 c.c. gelatine + 2 c.c. N/10-Pb (NO₃)₂ + water = 1.022×10^{-3} mhos. C. Conductivity of 9 c.c. gelatine + 2 c.c. N/10-KI + water = 1.479×10^{-3} mhos. D. Conductivity of 9 c.c. gelatine + 2 c.c. N/10-KNO₃ + water = 1.683×10^{-3} mhos.

Colour of mixture.	Time (hrs. min.).	Observed conductivity (mhos) of mixture 9 c.c. gelatine + 2 c.c. N/10-Pb (NO ₃) ₂ + 2 c.c. N/10-KI + water.	Observed conductivity (mhos) of PbI ₂ alone.	Calculated conductivity (mhos) if whole of PbI ₂ in ionic condition.	% of PbI ₂ in ionic condition.	
		E.	E - D.	B + C - D - A.		
Colourless	0.01 hr.	2.187×10^{-3}	0.504×10^{-3}	0.608×10^{-3}	83	
	0.30	2.179	0.496		82	
	0.45	2.187	0.504		83	
	1.00	2.179	0.496		82	
	1.15	2.184	0.501		82	
	1.30	2.173	0.490		81	
	1.45	2.187	0.504		83	
	2.00	2.179	0.496		82	
	2.30	2.187	0.504		83	
	3.00	2.179	0.496		82	
↓ Gradual change	3.30	2.184	0.501		82	
	4.00	2.173	0.490		81	
	4.30	2.187	0.504		83	
	4.50	2.179	0.496		82	
	5.00	2.179	0.496		82	
	↓ Apparance of greenish colour	5.45	2.187	0.504		83
		6.30	2.179	0.496		82
	↓ Gradual change	8.30	2.184	0.501		82
	↓ Appearance of yellow colour					

TABLE VI.

Temp. = 30° Total volume = 20 c.c.

pH of gelatine.	vol of gelatine.	N/10-Pb(NO ₃) ₂ and N/10-KI	Observed conductivity (mhos) of PbI ₂ alone in mixture.	Calculated conductivity (mhos) if whole of PbI ₂ in ionic condition.	% of PbI ₂ in ionic condition.
			E - D	B + C - D - A	
5.52	5.6 c.c.	2.0 c.c.	0.586 × 10 ⁻³	0.761 × 10 ⁻³	76
5.52	12.6	2.5	0.630	0.960	65
5.52	9.0	2.0	0.501	0.608	82
4.50	13.2	2.5	0.554	0.819	68
4.50	10.0	2.0	0.511	0.616	83

A well marked tendency for the combination of lead ions with gelatine is noticeable from the results given in Table V, for it is observed that the conductivity with lead nitrate is less than that with an equivalent amount of potassium iodide. These results also support the conclusion arrived at in the case of silver iodide in gelatine, namely that iodide ions combine more readily with gelatine than nitrate ions.

When lead nitrate in gelatine is mixed with potassium iodide in gelatine, the mixture is colourless. On allowing the mixture to stand, however, a colour develops which gradually changes from greenish to yellow. Simultaneously with these colour changes the mixture which is quite clear in the beginning develops turbidity and gradually the size of the particles also increases. However as in the case of silver chromate and silver iodide in gelatine, the colour changes are not due to any release of supersaturation, for whatever changes are to take place in the conductivity of the mixture occur immediately on mixing the solutions of lead nitrate and potassium iodide in gelatine. The conductivity also does not change at all with time. The cataphoretic experiments showed that at no stage the particles of lead iodide in gelatine are charged and it therefore appears to us that the insoluble portion of lead iodide in gelatine exists in a very highly dispersed condition as in the case of insoluble portion of silver chromate and of silver iodide in gelatine. In this case also the colour changes might be due to changes in the size of the particles.

It will appear from Table V that in this particular case about 40% of lead iodide exists in a finely dispersed condition and the remaining 60% in ionic condition. It is also noticed from Table VI that the amount of lead iodide which can remain in ionic condition in gelatine varies from (65% to 83%) with its p_H as well as with a change in the concentration of gelatine and of the reactants. Lead iodide thus behaves exactly as silver chromate in these respects. The present results however do not show if the fact that the inhibitive power of gelatine with reference to lead iodide is maximum for p_H value 5.00 has any significance in explaining the results about condition of lead iodide in gelatine.

Bolam (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1928, 24, 463; 1930, 26, 133) has come to the conclusion on the basis of conductivity and *e. m. f.* measurements that lead iodide is maintained in a highly supersaturated solution in agar gel. Chatterji and Dhar (*loc. cit.*) have discussed these results of Bolam and shown that the percentage of lead iodide in the ionic state decreases (from 99.3 to 52) as the concentration of lead iodide increases. We are of the opinion that this case is similar to the case of silver chromate and lead iodide in gelatine and the influence discussed under silver chromate (last para, under condition of Ag_2CrO_4) might also be responsible for these conflicting results. It thus seems necessary to investigate further these cases in a greater detail in order to get a correct idea about the condition of these substances in gel.

It will not be out of place to discuss here the meaning of the term "inhibition" as used by various investigators.

We (Desai and Naik, *loc. cit.*) have observed that gelatine of p_H 5.75 has the smallest inhibitive power with reference to Ag_2CrO_4 . According to Bolam and Donaldson (*loc. cit.*), the degree of supersaturation and therefore the inhibitive action of gelatine, probably, has an optimum value at p_H 5.0.

This conclusion of theirs is, however, difficult to reconcile with the inferences that can be drawn from Fig. 1 of their paper (*cf.* Bolam and Mackenzie, *loc. cit.*) as well as with our results namely that gelatine of p_H 5.75 has the smallest inhibitive power. If inhibition gives rise to supersaturation, one would have expected least supersaturation for gelatine of p_H 5.75 and greater for gelatine solutions of higher or lower p_H than 5.75. The results of Bolam and Donaldson however do not support this view. It thus appears

that the inhibition experiments (inhibition in the sense of power to prevent precipitation) cannot always be utilised to give an idea of the degree of supersaturation although they may do so in some cases and under certain circumstances. A highly supersaturated solution can only be produced if by some means the formation or the growth of crystallisation centres is prevented. If inhibition gives rise to a colloidal solution (Dhar and co-workers, *loc. cit.*), one would expect that the stability of the yellow sol containing negatively charged particles of Ag_2CrO_4 should regularly decrease with an increase of acidity of gelatine and therefore more and more of gelatine should be required for inhibition with a decrease of p_{H} ; our results however do not completely support the view for the inhibitive power of gelatine of p_{H} 5.75 to be minimum. Gelatine as an agent preventing precipitation of sparingly soluble substances generally (as in the case of Ag_2CrO_4 , AgI and PbI_2), can possibly function as producing either supersaturation or a colloidal solution by preventing aggregation of small particles to larger masses or particles in a very highly dispersed form or two of these three forms or even all the three forms simultaneously. Hedges ("Liesegang rings and other periodic structures" 1932, p. 62) has pointed out "it seems, on the whole, that sparingly soluble substances readily form relatively stable, highly supersaturated solutions in gels..... The formation of colloidal solutions is not ruled out, however, for such a system would probably be produced by a sudden release of supersaturation through some cause or other, just as relatively large crystals would be formed as a result of very slow release of supersaturation". To this one may also add a third possibility namely that gels may help in producing the sparingly soluble substances in a very highly dispersed form probably in molecular condition and that the union of these very fine particles by diffusion may ultimately give rise to larger visible particles. It thus appears necessary to investigate this problem further in order to understand clearly the difference in the rôle of gelatine in producing supersaturation and in preventing the precipitation of sparingly soluble substances and giving rise to colloidal solutions or in producing particles in a very highly dispersed form. In view of the conflicting results about the condition of silver chromate in gelatine, it is necessary to use the term "inhibition" in all cases of prevention of precipitation of sparingly soluble substances whether due to production of either supersaturation or a colloidal solution or particles having a very high

degree of dispersion or any two of the three or even all the three forms simultaneously instead of using that term to indicate only supersaturation as done by Bolam and Mackenzie (*loc. cit.*), Bolam and Desai (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1928, **24**, 50), Bolam and Donaldson (*loc. cit.*) and Desai and Nabar (*loc. cit.*, cf. also *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **9**, 141; *J. University of Bombay*, 1932, **1**, Part II, 28).

SUMMARY.

1. Experiments have been carried out to determine the condition of silver chromate, silver iodide and lead iodide in gelatine.

2. The conductivity results show that whatever changes in the conductivity are to take place occur immediately on mixing the solutions and that there is no gradual decrease of conductivity with changes in colour of the mixtures. The cataphoretic experiments do not show the presence of any charged colloidal particles in any of the cases. These results suggest that immediately the solutions are mixed some insoluble precipitate is produced, the particles of which are in a very highly dispersed condition—probably in molecular condition—and that changes in the colour of the mixtures are due to growth of these very fine particles into larger ones. A suggestion is made as to the likely causes of the conflicting results about the condition of silver chromate in gelatine.

3. The amount of silver chromate and lead iodide in ionic and highly dispersed condition varies to a large extent, depending on the p_{π} of gelatine and the concentration of gelatine and of the reactants, silver iodide does not show such a behaviour.

4. There is evidence to show that the tendency for the combination of various ions with gelatine is in the order

$$\begin{cases} \text{Ag} > \text{CrO}_4 > \text{NO}_3 \\ \text{Ag} > \text{I} > \text{NO}_3 \\ \text{Pb} > \text{I} > \text{NO}_3. \end{cases}$$

5. It is pointed out that the term "inhibition" should be used to indicate power to prevent precipitation generally whether it may be due to production of supersaturated solution or of colloidal solution or of particles in a very highly dispersed condition.

